

Research on the Evaluation of Enterprise-University-Research Cooperation Ability in Hubei Province

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Abstract : The measurement of enterprise-university-research cooperative efficiency has important meanings in improving the cooperative efficiency, strengthening the effective integration of regional resource, enhancing the ability of regional innovation and promoting the development of regional economy. The paper constructs the DEA method and DEA-Malmquist productivity index method to research the cooperation efficiency of Hubei by making comparisons with other provinces in China. The study found out the index of technology efficiency is 0.52 and the enterprise-university- research cooperative efficiency is Non-DEA efficient. To realize the DEA efficiency of Hubei province, the amount of 1652.596 R&D employees and 638.368 R&D employees' full time equivalence should be reduced or 137.89 billion yuan of new products' sales income be increased. Finally, it puts forward policy recommendations on existing problems to strengthen the standings of the cooperation, realize the effective application of the research results, and improve the level of management of enterprise-university-research cooperation efficiency.

Keywords : cooperation ability, DEA method, enterprise-university-research cooperation, Malmquist efficiency index

Conference Title : ICBEFSM 2014 : International Conference on Business, Economics, Financial Sciences and Management

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : June 19-20, 2014